

HILOM

A HOLISTIC WELLNESS RETREAT AND RECREATION COMPLEX

BAGAC, BATAAN, PHILIPPINES

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The topic of Health and Wellness is gaining more popularity because of recent covid-19 pandemic. Physical and psychological stressors have been more common on society because from the hardships and isolation brought by the illness. As a result, the importance of mental and physical health has risen. Shifts are occurring within the workplace and educational world.

The awareness on health and wellness has been increased, also the demand of spaces and facilities that is related to treatment for health. Wellness retreat and recreation complexes are become significantly popular for individuals who seeks to enhance their well-being in a serene and peaceful environment. These facilities offer physical and fitness programs, recreational activities, healing pools, counseling, accommodation, mindfulness and spiritual practices.

DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

Organic architecture seeks superior sense of use and a finer sense of comfort, expressed in organic simplicity.

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BUILDING MATERIALS

BAMBOO	ENGINEERED WOOD	LOW-E GLASS	WOOD CLADDING
CONCRETE	WOOD LOUVERS	SOLAR PANELS	POLISHED CONCRETE PANEL
STEEL	BRICKS	RAINWATER COLLECTOR	NIPA SHINGLES

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- To integrate natural environment into the design to foster connection with nature that enhances well-being.
- To design that encourages physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being through nature, relaxation, and recreational activities.
- To implement sustainable eco-friendly building materials to promote sustainability in the complex.
- To develop a complex that caters all the need of end users.
- To ensure that the design is inclusive and accessible, accommodating various age groups, gender and people with disability.

DESIGN OBJECTIVES

- To maximize the use of natural elements of environment such as light and greenery to promote connection with nature and occupants.
- To design dedicated to activities of wellness zones such as yoga, meditation, spa areas, healing pools, fitness gym and recreational zones.
- To use sustainable eco-friendly building materials that is locally available to promote green architecture.
- To focus on acoustics, light and ventilation, and climate to ensure comfort and tranquility.
- To develop a complex that adheres to visual language through materials, colors and forms.

DESIGN CRITERIA

- Incorporate Large E windows to improve natural light and ventilation. Create a sustainable and flexible
- multi-functional space for wellness activities to improve the mood and health of every individual like spas, fitness gym and specialized zones. Utilize local and sustainable materials such as bamboo, natural wood, and incorporate renewable energy systems like solar panels and rainwater collector. Implement
- materials, sound-absorbing building promote natural ventilation and passive solar design to enhance comfort and tranquility for the guests.
- Choose right building materials and color palette that reflect a cohesive aesthetic and adapt in the natural surroundings to maintain consistency in architectural forms throughout the complex.

COLOR PALLETTE

DESIGN CONSIDERATION

AESTHETIC	ACCESSIBILITY	HARMONY
SUSTAINABILITY	COMFORT	DURABILITY
CIRCULATION	EFFICIENCY	VENTILATION

FORM CONCEPT

The project draws inspiration from the BAHAY KUBO (INDIGENOUS HOUSES) The nipa hut (English: nipa hut) or hut is a traditional house in the Philippines. The nipa hut is recognized as the national house of the Philippines. It is made from local materials, its walls are usually made of bamboo, wood, cogon or thatch and its roof from nipa or palm leaves.

DESIGN CONCEPT

The design concept is Nature-Centered Design: By utilizing biophilic design principles the complex will have an amazing harmonious environment that enhances the mental, physical and spiritual well-being. The retreat will emphasize the healing properties of nature through the natural elements such as water, plants and light.